

The Environmental Stress Corrosion Cracking of Glass Fibre Reinforced Polyester and Epoxy Composites

F. R. Jones, J. W. Rock, A. R. Wheatley, J. E. Bailey
Department of Metallurgy and Materials Technology, University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH, U.K.

ABSTRACT

The ESCC of epoxy and polyester glass fibre 0° and $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ composites has been studied. The polyester resin protects the fibres in that the coupons have longer failure times than single filaments. Post-curing decreases the ESCC resistance of the composite. In contrast, the transverse cracking strain of the $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ epoxy laminates is reduced, under the influence of the stress and the environment, with the result that at strains $>0.15\%$ the coupons had similar failure times to those for single fibres. At lower strains, fracture of the unimmersed half of the coupon occurs under the apparent influence of crystalline corrosion products.

INTRODUCTION

Glass fibre reinforced unsaturated polyester resins are becoming increasingly used in applications in which the material is in contact with acidic environments, such as process plant equipment, storage vessels and sewage pipes. GRP shows good chemical resistance to aqueous acids (1) but in the presence of a stress, rapid fracture can occur (2,3). The environmental stress corrosion cracking of these composite materials is to some measure determined by the susceptibility of E-glass fibre both to corrosion and stress corrosion (4,5). It has now been well established that stress corrosion fracture surfaces are essentially planar and normal to the applied stress with little evidence of fibre pullout (2,3,6-11). An explanation of the planar fracture surfaces, in terms of a short stress transfer length is given by Kelly et al from a comparison of the stress rupture of glass fibre strands and impregnated bundles (10,11). Hogg and Hull (6,7) have identified three stages in the stress corrosion cracking of pipes and demonstrated that stress and strain corrosion cracking are the same phenomenon.

We (12) have reported the nucleation of environmental stress corrosion cracking (ESCC) of polyester crossply coupons, in 4-point bend, at transverse cracks formed at $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface. These propagate into the load bearing tensile 0° ply under the influence of the environment (13). Since the magnitude of the thermal strains determine the transverse cracking strain and have ESCC

resistance (12) we concluded that the transverse cracks were effective notches for the stress corrosion of the 0° ply. We have, therefore, extended our study to both $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ and 0° coupons under a constant tensile load.

In addition, the more chemically resistant unsaturated polyester resins are based on Bisphenol 'A' intermediately so that an anhydride cured epoxy resin could be considered to be a model matrix resin. Furthermore $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ composites from Epikote 828 cured with NMA and reinforced with Silenka 051P E-glass fibres have been shown to exhibit fibre-matrix debonding at lower strain than that for transverse cracking (14), enabling interfacial effects to be studied. In this paper therefore, we present a comparison of the ESCC of the glass fibre reinforced resins having ester links; one an unsaturated isophthalic and the other an anhydride cured epoxide with single glass fibres.

EXPERIMENTAL

The laminates were prepared from Silenka E-glass fibre 051P (1200 tex) by methods similar to those described elsewhere (12,18). Epikote 828 (Shell Ltd.) was cured with 80phr NMA and 1.5phr BDMA at 100°C for 3h and at 150°C for 3h. The softening point was 140°C (16). Crystic 272 was cured with 2phr Catalyst M and 0.25% Accelerator E (Scott-Bader Ltd.) for 172h at room temperature or post-cured at 80°C for 3h.

'Open' and 'closed' environmental tubes were attached to the 2 cm wide coupons so that only half was unimmersed. Either constant or dynamic tensile loads were applied. Single glass filaments, whose diameters were determined by laser refraction were fully immersed during stress corrosion (13,15). 0.5M and 1.0M aqueous H_2SO_4 were used.

RESULTS

The $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ model composite has been described previously (14). In these experiments the thickness of the outer 0° ply was equal to half that of the inner 90° ply and was approximately 1 mm. The environmental stress corrosion cracking (ESCC) of these glass fibre laminates has been studied in tension under a constant load. At low strains of approximately 0.2% the epoxy glass laminates fractured with 24 hours whereas the polyester/glass coupons were still intact after 3 months. The latter however, developed a series of transverse edge-cracks but these did not lead to fracture of the 0° load bearing plies (17).

Environmental Stress Corrosion Cracking of Epoxy/Glass Laminates

The stress corrosion of the load bearing plies may occur either within the environment, termed Mode I, or in the unimmersed part of the specimen, termed Mode II. The mode of failure which occurs is dependent upon the type of environmental cell, the nature of the environmental, and the initial applied strain. The difference between the two types of failures is illustrated in Fig. 1. Mode I failures of $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ coupons occur by fracture of the longitudinal plies adjacent to one of the early microcracks in the transverse ply. In Fig. 1a the initial applied strain was sufficient to induce transverse cracking and the transverse crack responsible for failure is indicated. However, at lower strains such that no transverse cracks would be produced in air, cracks are seen to form at the edge of the coupon, in contact with the aqueous acid, and propagate into the transverse ply. These lead to Mode I fracture in the 'closed' cell but in the 'open' cell at strains $>0.15\%$ Mode II occurs at an earlier time, as shown in Fig. 2. Fig. 1c shows that Mode I failure of the 0° unidirectional occurs by random nucleation of ESCC cracks which coalesce and form a stepped fracture surface (13). The failure times in Fig. 3 correlate closely with those for the $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ cross-ply coupons, when the applied strain is calculated assuming the cracked 90° ply carries no load. Fig. 4 demonstrates that the single glass filaments fail catastrophically within similar immersion times.

Fig.1. TYPES OF ENVIRONMENTAL STRESS CRACKING OF EPOXY G.R.P.
a, c, e are $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ and b, d are 0° coupons

If crossply coupons are totally immersed in 0.5M aqueous sulphuric acid there is no tendency for edge-cracks to form and acid attack is limited to the external faces of the laminate, where only the surface glass fibres show signs of damage. However, when the laminate is only half immersed in aqueous sulphuric acid in an 'open' cell, without an applied load, the unimmersed portion of the laminate shows both splitting of the 0° and transverse cracking of the 90° plies (termed Mode III damage) after approximately 72 hours. The immersed half remains unaffected and quite transparent (Fig. 1e). Furthermore, small crystals are seen to grow on the unimmersed edges of the coupon. With 1M aqueous hydrochloric acid only minor damage occurs after several weeks.

Environmental Stress Corrosion Cracking of Polyester/Glass Laminates

The most striking result of these experiments is the much longer failure times and higher strains involved for Mode I fractures (Fig.3), the absence of Mode II and that nature of edge damage compared to the epoxy laminates. The $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ coupons showed a marked tendency to generate large numbers of small edge-cracks at applied strains less than that for transverse cracking and even the cold-cured samples, when the applied stress is maximised, did not fracture. Only heavily transverse cracked coupons with applied strains $>0.5\%$ failed catastrophically. The close correlation between the failure times of 0° and $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ coupons demonstrates that the failure mechanisms are similar to those of the epoxy composites, in which the transverse cracks throw the load on to the 0° plies. This result is in contrast to the ESCC under bending loads where the transverse cracks nucleate a more rapid failure (13). Fig. 3 also demonstrates that the post-cured coupons are less resistant.

DISCUSSION

Mode I Failures

When the 90° ply of a crossply laminate fractures, the load that it supported is thrown onto the longitudinal plies, at a place adjacent to the transverse crack. Away from the transverse crack the stress is transferred back into the 90° plies causing a further fracture of the transverse ply when an additional increment makes it greater than the transverse failure strain. Thus the shear lag model has been used successfully to predict the multiple cracking behaviour

of these laminates (18), Transverse cracks may also act as notches for the nucleation of stress corrosion cracks. Since the fracture of 0° unidirectional laminates from both resin systems occurs within the same immersion time as equivalent crossply laminates (Fig. 3) we conclude that the effect of a transverse crack is simply to increase the load on the longitudinal plies by a calculable increment and not to reduce the failure times, which would be the consequence of a notch. This contrasts with the failure mechanism of the same polyester composite in 4-point bend where the transverse cracks have been shown to initiate stress corrosion cracks at $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface (12,13).

However the failure times of the epoxy and polyester composites differ significantly. Most noticeable is the nature of the stress corrosion at applied strains less than that for transverse cracking in air. In the polyester coupons small ESCC cracks form in the tensile 0° faces but within the timescale of these experiments (>100 days) no catastrophic fractures have been observed. In addition, edge-cracks grow in the transverse ply under the influence of the stress and the corrodent, which do not appear to lead-up the longitudinal ply, as shown by a lack of localised ESCC nuclei in the vicinity of them. Microscopy has demonstrated that these cracks do not span the thickness of the transverse ply (17). Some do however appear to run completely across the width. In contrast however, the ESCC fracture of the 0° plies of the epoxy coupons at these low strains occurs adjacent to one of the early edge-cracks. These edge-cracks therefore, do load-up the 0° plies and appear to behave like normal transverse cracks formed in air and the inference is that the transverse cracking strain is reduced, under the influence of the environment.

The Transverse Cracking Strain of the Epoxy Composites in the Environment

In order to determine the transverse failure strain under stress corrosion conditions, the following analysis was used. After Bailey and Parvisi (18) the additional stress in the 0° plies in the plane of the transverse crack, $\Delta \sigma_o$ is given by the modified shear-lag theory.

$$\Delta \sigma_o = \epsilon_{t\ell u} E_t d [1 + \exp(-\phi^{1/2} t) - 2 \exp(-\phi^{1/2} t/2)]/b \quad \text{----(1)}$$

where $\phi = E_c G_t (b+d)/E_t E_t b d^2$ and $\epsilon_{t\ell u}$ is the transverse ply cracking strain, E_c , E_t and E_l are the Young's moduli of the composite and longitudinal and transverse plies respectively. G_t is the shear modulus of the transverse ply in the longitudinal direction, b and d are thicknesses of the longitudinal and semi-transverse plies. t is the transverse crack spacing.

$$\Delta \sigma_o = \chi \sigma_a \quad \text{----(2)}$$

where $\chi = (b+d)/b - (E_l/E_c)$ and σ_a = applied stress. Rearrangement of (1) and (2) and placing $\psi = \chi b/\epsilon_{t\ell u} E_t d$ we get

$$1/\psi \sigma_a = [1 + \exp(-\phi^{1/2} t) - 2 \exp(-\phi^{1/2} t/2)] \quad \text{----(3)}$$

Equation (3) is a quadratic expression in $\exp(-\phi^{1/2} t)$ whose solution is given by

$$-\phi^{1/2} t/2 = \ln(1 \pm \sigma_a^{-1/2} \psi^{-1/2}) \quad \text{----(4)}$$

Equation (4) predicts a linear relationship between the crack spacing, t and $\ln(1/(1 \pm \sigma_a^{-1/2} \psi^{-1/2}))$ with slope $2/\phi^{1/2}$. Fig. 5 gives a plot of the experimental crack spacing for the epoxy/glass coupons compared to equation (4) with $\epsilon_{t\ell u}$ for the best fit to the data. $\epsilon_{t\ell u}$ is therefore determined from the cracking pattern of the coupon in the dynamic test, unperturbed by the nucleation of transverse cracks at gross laminate defects. $\epsilon_{t\ell u}^I$ was found to be 0.38%.

FIG. 2. ESOC Failure Times of Epoxy $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ Coupons in Open (●) and Closed (■) Cells. ϵ_a is that in the 0° Piles.

FIG. 3. Comparison of the ESOC of Epoxy $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ (●), $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ (■); Polyester 0° (○), $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ (◐). The Post-Cure Temperature is given.

FIG. 5. Transverse Crack Spacing as a Function of An ($1/(12 \sigma^2 \phi^2)$) According to Equation 4. In Air (●) $\epsilon_{tLu} = 0.38\%$; H_2SO_4 aq. (■) $\epsilon_{tLu} = 0.1\%$.

FIG. 4. Comparison of Mode I Failure Times Epoxy $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ (■), $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ (◐) with Single Glass Filaments (●).

Fig. 5 also includes the transverse crack spacing from a tensile test in which the coupon is half immersed in aqueous sulphuric acid. From the best fit to the data the transverse cracking strain in the environment $\epsilon_{t\ell y}^e$ was found to be $\approx 0.1\%$. The dry half of the coupon had a crack spacing typical of the test in air. Similar experiments with the polyester composite showed no discernable reduction in the transverse cracking strain.

The transverse cracking in air of this epoxy composite has been previously shown to be preceded by debonds at individual fibres, which coalesce to form a transverse crack at a higher strain. It follows therefore, that either stress corrosion of the resin, or interface, or both, occurs. The Mode III damage and the Mode II failure described strongly imply that stress corrosion of the interface occurs. In order to estimate the debonding strain in the environment we make use of equation 5 (14).

$$\epsilon_{tu}^b / \epsilon_{tu}^{nb} = 1 / (1 - V_f) \quad \text{---- (5)}$$

where V_f = fibre volume fraction. Since V_f of the epoxy coupons was 55% this ratio should be ≈ 2 . Debonding was shown to be responsible for the first 'knee' in the stress-strain curve at 0.25% and $\epsilon_{t\ell u} = 0.55\%$. $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ was also reported as 0.08% (14). Therefore

$$\epsilon_{tu}^b / \epsilon_{tu}^{nb} = (\epsilon_{t\ell u} + \epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}) / \epsilon_{tu}^b - (\epsilon_{db} + \epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}) = 0.63 / 0.3 \approx 2 \quad \text{---- (6)}$$

where ϵ_{db}^b , ϵ_{tu}^b and ϵ_{tu}^{nb} are respectively the debonding strain, and failure strains of the bonded and non-bonded transverse ply.

The higher softening point of the coupons used in this study meant that $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th} = 0.22\%$ and that $\epsilon_{t\ell u} = 0.28\%$. Equation 6 predicts that $\epsilon_{db} = 0.03\%$ which is very close to the observed whitening strain at 0.05%. Fig. 5 shows that $\epsilon_{t\ell u}$ is reduced to at least 0.1% during a dynamic tensile test whereas $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ is not reduced significantly over much longer periods in the environment, as demonstrated by relatively slow increase in the radius curvature of a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beam (15). The debonding strain therefore will also be reduced and equation 6 predicts that the coupon will debond in the environment. Furthermore, for this laminate configuration $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ is equivalent to the thermal strain in transverse direction of the longitudinal ply $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$. It follows therefore that under the influence of the environment and stress, the longitudinal plies will also become debonded and the equivalent stress corrosion failure times of the single glass fibres and the epoxy crossply laminates can be understood by the stress-corrosion of the interface leading to a rapid transport of H_2SO_4 . The equivalent failure times for 0° and $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ coupons suggests that diffusion is probably more important than transport along a transverse crack to the interface. Menges and Gitschner (19) show that diffusion through the $\approx 5 \mu m$ layers of the resin between the fibres will have occurred during the time scale of these experiments.

Since the stressed 0° epoxy coupons at strains $>0.2\%$ also have similar ESCC failure times as the single glass fibres, we conclude that debonding can also occur. The mechanism of these failures is still uncertain but the implication is that the stress state derived either from the longitudinal thermal, Poisson or swelling strains can cause debonding or resin cracking in the vicinity of the fibres. These failures are the subject of further investigation.

The polyester coupons are less susceptible to ESCC cracking than the equivalent epoxy composites. The result cannot be accounted for by a volume fraction effect since it has been possible to produce the composites with similar compositions. However, the difference in thermal strains which exist in post-cured coupons might be expected to improve the ESCC resistance by putting the fibres into compression. Furthermore, since the transverse ply interface does not appear to be sensitive to stress corrosion it seems likely that the diffusion of the acid through the resin, which is probably stress enhanced, is the most important factor.

Mode II Failure and Mode III Damage. Reproducible Mode II failures illustrated in Fig. 1 have so far been confined to the epoxy glass coupons and always occur at low applied strains in both 0° unidirectional and crossply laminates, in the unimmersed half of the coupon after apparently less time than an equivalent Mode I failure (Fig. 2). Various possible mechanisms such as attack by acid vapour and/or oxygen have been tested but it is always observed that crystalline deposits feature in the fracture surface and on the edge of the coupon. Whereas the former invariably are rich in calcium the latter are totally based on aluminium and traces of potassium. These results demonstrate the crystallisation of the less soluble calcium sulphate within the laminate and the more soluble aluminium sulphate and the potassium and sodium aluminium sulphates on the exposed edges. Mode II fractures are also inhibited in the closed cell when the atmosphere is saturated with water vapour. Furthermore, in aqueous 1M HCl Mode I failure occurs at these low strains in the 'open' cell. These experiments show that Mode II is inhibited when the calcium salts remain soluble. In addition, the Mode III damage can occur in the whole specimen when half is immersed in phosphoric acid whose calcium salt is much less soluble than calcium sulphate. We suggest therefore that the H_2SO_4 is transported through the debonded immersed half of an epoxy $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ coupon to the unimmersed half, where the interface is still intact. Wicking is no longer possible and the environment diffuses into or permeates through the 'dry' region. The change in concentration causes the lowly soluble glass corrosion products to precipitate. The more soluble ions can be transported to the edge of the coupon. Continuous crystallisation of calcium sulphate at the glass/resin interface produces an additional stress which causes the Mode II crack to run from the edge of the coupon. In the absence of a stress σ_{ct}^{th} is sufficient to environmentally debond the 0° fibres, which are in compression so that only progressive transverse and longitudinal cracking occurs. A strain of 0.05% is sufficient for Mode II. The Mode II failure of the 0° epoxy coupons can be similarly explained.

CONCLUSIONS

The prime cause of ESCC fractures of GRP is the susceptibility of the glass fibres to stress corrosion cracking in acidic environments (4,5). Therefore the prime function of the resin is to protect the glass fibres. In this study we have identified different ESCC mechanisms which can cause complete fracture of the GRP under the combined influence of aqueous sulphuric acid and an applied stress. Two composite systems based on 'polyester' matrices, one a conventional unsaturated polyester and the other an anhydride cured epoxide and an epoxy/polyester compatible glass. Important differences in the rate of stress corrosion cracking have been identified. The failure mechanism of the epoxy laminate demonstrates that the interface can also be prone to stress corrosion cracking and that this is the major factor since the fibres become accessible. Low strain fractures can also occur when diffusion along the fibre interface dominates the corrosion progress.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We wish to thank the SERC for an equipment grant, a research studentship (J.W.R), the Polymer Engineering Directorate for a research fellowship (A.R.W), Scott-Bader and Co Ltd. for the polyester resin and Silenka (UK) Ltd. for the glass fibre.

REFERENCES

1. Norwood, L.S. and Farebrother, T., "The Importance of the Anti-corrosion Barrier Layer in GRP Process Plant Applications", Symp. Reinf. Plast. in Anti-corrosion Applications, National Engineering Laboratory, Glasgow 1979, paper 8.
2. Barker, H.A., Baird-Smith, I.G., and Jones, F.R. "Larger Diameter GRP pipes in Civil Engineering - The Influence of Corrosive Environments", Symp. Reinf. Plast. in Anti-corrosion Applications, N.E.L. Glasgow 1979, paper 12.

3. Roberts, R.C. "Design Strain and Failure Mechanisms of GRP in a Chemical Environment", Reinf. Plast. Congress (BPF), Brighton 1978, paper 19.
4. Metcalf, A.G. and Schmitz, G.K. "Mechanisms of Stress Corrosion in E-glass Filaments", Glass Tech. 13, 1972, p5-16.
5. Metcalf, A.G., Gulden, Mary E. and Schmitz, G.K. "Spontaneous Cracking of Glass Filaments", Glass Tech. 12, 1974, p15-23.
6. Hogg, P.J. and Hull, D., "Micromechanisms of Crack Growth in Composite Materials Under Corrosive Environments", Metals Science, 1980, p441-449.
7. Hull, D. and Hogg, P.J. "Nucleation and Propagation of Cracks during Strain Corrosion of GRP" in Advances in Composite Materials (Ed. Bunsell, A.R. et al), Pergamon, Vol.1, 1980, p543-555.
8. Hogg, P.J., Hull, D. and Legg, M.J. "Failure of GRP in Corrosive Environments" in Composite Structures (Ed. Marshall, I.H.) App. Sci. 1980, p 106-122.
9. Collins, H.H. "Strain Corrosion Cracking of GRP Laminates", Plast. Rubb. Mat. and Appl., 1978, p6-10.
10. Aveston, J., Kelly, A. and Sillwood, J.M. "Long Term Strength of Glass Reinforced Plastics in Wet Environments" in Advances in Composite Materials, Pergamon, Vol.1, p556-568.
11. Kelly, A. and McCartney, L.N. "Failure by Stress Corrosion of Bundles of Fibres", Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A 374, 1981, p475-489.
12. Jones, F.R., Wheatley, A.R. and Bailey, J.E. "The Effect of Thermal Strains on the Microcracking and Stress Corrosion Behaviour of GRP" in Composite Structures (Ed. Marshall, I.H.) App. Sci. 1980, p415-429.
13. Jones, F.R., Rock, J.W., Wheatley, A.R. and Bailey, J.E. "Environmental Stress Corrosion Cracking of GRP", Reinf. Plast. Congress (BPF), Brighton, 1982.
14. Bailey, J.E. and Parvizi, A. "On Fibre Debonding Effects and the Mechanism of Transverse-Ply Failure Strain in Cross-ply Laminates of Glass Fibre Composites", J. Mat. Sci. 16, 1981, p649-659.
15. Jones, F.R. and Rock, J.W. in preparation.
16. Jones, F.R. and Mulheron, M.J. "Origins of Thermal Strains in Polyester Composites", ICCM 4, Japan, 1982.
17. Bailey, J.E., Fryer, T.M.W. and Jones, F.R. "Environmental Stress-Corrosion Edge-Cracking of Glass Reinforced Polyesters" in Advances in Composite Materials, Pergamon, Vol.1, p514-528.
18. Parvizi, A. and Bailey, J.E. "On Multiple Transverse Cracking in Glass Fibre Epoxy Cross-ply Laminates", J. Mat. Sci. 13, 1978, p2131-2136.
19. Menges, G. and Gitschner, H.W. " Sorption Behaviour of Glass Fibre Reinforced Composite" in Advances in Composite Materials, Pergamon, Vol.1, p25-48.